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Synthesis and Ion Exchange Properties of New Series of Inorganic Ion Exchangers : VII Hydrous Cerium (IV), Oxide and Thorium Antimonate.

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IN continuation of our work on the development of new inorganic ion exchangers¹⁻⁶, we have found hydrous cerium (IV) oxide and thorium antimonate to have useful ion exchange properties. These belong to the classes of hydrous oxides of metals and insoluble salts of polybasic metals respectively⁷. The present communication summarises our preliminary studies on these inorganic ion exchangers.

Experimental

Reagents: All the chemicals used were of analar grade (B.D.H. or S. Merck).

Apparatus: pH measurements were made with an Elico Model 10 pH meter, Hyderabad, India Spectromom 2.2 (Hungary) was used for spectrophotometric work.

Synthesis: Hydrous cerium (IV) oxide of two different forms were prepared by mixing ceric sulfate and sodium hydroxide solutions in different ratios at room temperature. Crystalline variety was obtained using the normal order of addition of the reagents (ceric sulphate/sodium hydroxide) while amorphous form was obtained by reversing the order of addition (sodium hydroxide/ceric sulphate). In each case the mixture was digested for 2 hr. at room temperature.

Thorium antimonate was prepared by mixing thorium nitrate and potassium pyroantimonate solutions in nitric acid and also by mixing thorium nitrate and antimony pentachloride solutions in different ratios at room temperature. The mixture was digested for 2 hr. at room temperature.

Results and Discussion

The compositions of both hydrous cerium (IV) dioxide and thorium antimonate were established by analysis by standard methods. The former had CeO₂ : H₂O ratios 2.58 (crystalline) and 3.00 (amorphous) while the latter had Sb. The ratios 3.67, 4.27 etc. These products are fairly stable in acids of moderate concentrations (upto 0.5 M) and more stable in water and alkali at room temperature.

pH titration curves were obtained by following the method of Topp and Peppers⁸ by shaking intermittently a known weight of the exchanger with different amounts of alkali, MoH (M=Li, Na or K) plus alkali sulphate. The curves indicate monofunctional behaviour of the exchangers. The ion exchange capacities of the exchangers at different pH were determined from the pH titrations. The ion exchange capacities follow the sequence: Li⁺ < Na⁺ < K⁺ < NH₄⁺, which agree with the order of decreasing hydrated ionic radius in the series. With increase in pH, there is increase in the ion exchange capacity values.

Distribution coefficient values of various metal ions were measured at optimum pH 6-8 as reported in our earlier papers¹⁻⁶ and on the basis of these values several selective ion exchange separation schemes have been worked out. Details of these investigations will be published elsewhere.

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Copper Thiomalate as an Indicator in the Volumetric Estimation of Rare Earths

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RECENTLY¹ it was reported that copper-thiomalate can be effectively used as an indicator in the volumetric estimation of Al(III), Ga(III) and In(III). The same metal indicator can be successfully employed in

the volumetric determination of Nd(III), Sm(III), Gd(III) and Y(III) in the pH range 4.8 and 5. The aliquots containing Nd(III), Sm(III) Gd(III) and Y(III) when titrated against standard EDTA solution in the presence of copper-thiomalate, give a sharp end point from violet to blue. The concentration range for the accurate determination of these metals is 1 to 40 mgs of Nd, 40 to 100 mgs of Sm, 1 to 60 mgs of Gd and 4 to 30 mgs of Y. When the results were compared with the results obtained using the conventional² indicator, they were found to be satisfactory. The following ions like Br^- , MnO_4^- , ClO_4^{2-} , $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{4-}$, CNS^- , CN^- , $\text{S}_2\text{O}_3^{2-}$, MoO_4^- , PO_4^{3-} , $\text{C}_2\text{O}_4^{2-}$ interfere seriously. Small traces of NO_2^- increase the sharpness of the end point. The relatively cheaper indicator and sharp end point are the special features of the proposed method.

Procedure :

To the aliquot of the solutions containing Nd(III), Sm(III), Gd(III) or Y(III) (the range mentioned above) 1 ml of Cu(II) solution (0.1M) and 1ml of 1% aqueous solution of thiomalic acid were added. The pH of the mixture was adjusted between 4.8 and 5 with acetate buffer. The mixture was then titrated against standard EDTA solution till the colour changed from violet to blue. The amount of EDTA for 1 ml of Cu(II) being known, amount of metal was calculated.

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Chemical Investigation of *Coleus aromaticus* Benth. Part II

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β -sitosterol- β -D-glucoside and 5, 4'-di-hydroxy, 6, 7-dimethoxy flavone (cirsimaritin) have been isolated from the leaves of *Coleus aromaticus* (family—Labiatae).

The isolation of a few components have been reported earlier by various workers¹⁻⁵ from this plant.

Experimental

The percolation of air-dried powdered leaves (7 kg.) was carried out with 75% ethanol and the alcoholic extract was concentrated under reduced pressure at 50°. The concentrate was successively fractionated with hexane, ethylacetate and n-butanol.

Hexane fraction : The compounds isolated from hexane soluble fraction have already been reported by us⁶.

Ethyl acetate fraction : The ethylacetate soluble residue (25 g.) was chromatographed over silicagel (500 g.) and eluted successively with benzene, benzene : ethylacetate (3 : 1), benzene : ethylacetate (1 : 1) and ethylacetate.

Benzene : ethylacetate (3:1) eluate gave a compound which crystallized from methanol as light yellow needles, m. p. 255-6°. (Found : C, 64.5; H, 4.9. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_6$ requires C, 64.9; H, 4.45%). The IR spectra showed characteristic peaks at 3280 (O—H); 1660 (C=O); 1600, 1570 (C—C) and 1245 (C—O) cm^{-1} . The compound gave positive test for flavonoids (pink colour with magnesium and hydrochloric acid). λ_{max} 220, 276 (band II), 333 (band I), (MeOH); 221, 301, 361 (AlCl_3) 238, 276, 395 (NaOMe); 220, 276, 333 nm (NaOAc and NaOAc+boric acid). The absence of bathochromic shift in band II in the presence of NaOAc indicated the absence of 7-hydroxyl group in the flavone molecule. Since no shift in any band occurred with boric acid buffer, this ruled out the possibility of ortho-di-hydroxyl grouping in the molecule. A bathochromic shift of 28 nm in band I and 25 nm in band II in the presence of AlCl_3 indicated the presence of —OH group either at C-5 or at C-3. A bathochromic shift of 62 nm in band I without a decrease in intensity in the presence of NaOMe showed the presence of free 4'-hydroxyl group in the molecule. Mass spectrum : (m/e) : 314 (M^+), 299 ($\text{M}-\text{C I}_3$), 286 ($\text{M}-\text{CO}$), 271 ($286-\text{CH}_3$), 254 ($271-\text{OH}$), 196 ($\text{M}-118$), 168 ($196-\text{CO}$), 153 ($168-\text{CH}_3$).

The compound was acetylated by Ac_2O pyridine at room temperature. The product thus obtained was purified by preparative TLC and the pure acetyl derivative was crystallized from methanol, m.p. 160°-61°, IR (KBr), 1748 (C=O) cm^{-1} . The marked shift in the stretching frequency of C=O group in the acetyl derivative in due to the absence of hydrogen bonding which existed in the original compound. NMR (CDCl_3) ; τ 7.6 δ , 7.54 (3 H each, s, OCOCH_3) ; 6.13, 6.0 (3H each, s, OCH_3) ; 3.5 (H, s, 3-H) 3.13 (1H, s, 8-H) ; 2.81 (2H, d, J=9Hz) ; 2.18 (2H, d, J=9Hz). The nmr signal at τ value 3.5 showed the presence of C-3 proton and, therefore, one hydroxyl group is present at C-5. Low field absorption by two protons (doublets) at τ 2.81 and two protons (doublets) at τ 2.18 indicated that the —OH group of ring B is present at C-4'. The positioning of —OH group at C-4' makes available two sets of doublets of 3'-H, 5'-H and 2'-H, 6'-H. The compound gave positive test with Gibb's reagent indicating the presence of unsubstituted CH para to a phenolic group. Thus two methoxy groups can be positioned at C-6 and C-7. On the basis of these physico-chemical evidences the compound was assigned to be 5, 4'-di-hydroxy, 6, 7-di-methoxy flavone⁷ (cirsimaritin).

Since the authentic sample of cirsimaritin was not available, the direct comparison by co TLC, m. m. p. determination and superimposable IR spectra could not be done.